

THE NEGATIVE EFFECT OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC ON GLOBAL FINANCIAL MARKETS

Akhmedova Shokhistakhon Asliddin kizi

(Bachelor's degree student, Tashkent Institute of Finance)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7439673>

ABSTRACT: Today, no country is immune to the negative effects of the COVID-19 pandemic, not only economically but also socially.

This article analyzes the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the global financial markets, which has left behind all the financial and economic crises in history with negative consequences. In particular, the negative effects of the pandemic on international stock markets were presented, and the author made detailed analysis about these consequences.

KEY WORDS: COVID-19 pandemic, economic recession, GDP, financial markets, government bonds, advanced economy, emerging market and developing economies, monetary policy.

INTRODUCTION: The COVID-19 pandemic poses unprecedented challenges to health, economic and financial sustainability. Of course, in such a situation, the primary goal is to save human lives. However, the necessary measures taken to limit the spread of the virus are leading to a sharp decline in economic activity. As a result, in just three months, the forecast for 2020 has shrunk sharply from the expected 3 percent increase globally to a negative 3 percent, far exceeding the product losses seen during the 2008-2009 global financial crisis. The extent of the impact of the crisis on the global economy and the timing of the economy's recovery are very uncertain. This crisis poses a serious threat to the stability of the global financial system. Following the outbreak of COVID-19, financial conditions have deteriorated at an unprecedented rate, leading to some "cracks" in global financial markets. Volatility in the market has intensified and borrowing costs have increased as a result of widespread defaults. Tensions have arisen in key financing markets, including the global financing market for the U.S. dollar. The outflows of large capitals have also exacerbated various shocks in the domestic markets of countries in emerging market economies. These changes could put pressure on banks as borrowers become unable to repay their debts, leading to a halt in credit markets over a period of time. Long-term dislocation in financial markets can cause panic among financial institutions and in turn lead to a credit crisis for non-financial borrowers and exacerbate the economic crisis.

LITERATURE REVIEW: The COVID-19 pandemic has affected all financial markets around the world, in particular, the stock price trend has declined

significantly and steadily. The Dow Jones and S&P from the United States are among the financial markets facing such a situation. In Daily FT (March 2020) which is one of the most well-known financial magazines, it is supported the fact stating that, “The Dow Jones, and S&P both of which take into account the share prices of a variety of companies in the US have dropped by over 20%”.

Globally, financial markets are experiencing some closures and stock prices are falling significantly due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The pandemic has shifted financial markets to completely different trade routes that affect the world economy. In particular, Colombo stock exchanges sometimes close their businesses and stock prices fall significantly. In Daily FT (March 2020) it is suggested that, “Even the Colombo Stock Exchange has seen almost a 9% drop in its All Share Price Index over the course of the last week, and has been forced to close trading three times during this week”.

Another evidence of the impact of the pandemic on global financial markets is the Nikkei, which trades on the Tokyo Stock Exchange. The trend of market price of Nikkei as well experienced the volatility of the share prices and mostly a downward trend throughout since the outbreak of the COVID – 19. In Daily FT (March 2020) it is elaborated that, “Similarly, the Nikkei, which takes into account share prices of companies in the Tokyo Stock Exchange has also dropped significantly in the last few days”. The most well-known economic experts suggested that the current pandemic has a serious impact on the global economy, with the attention that the world is going to the global recession. A global recession is a situation where the world production goes down with the effect of employment which means companies production will be affected and falls down and people will lose employment while the import and exportation activities will be affected by the recession worldwide. In Euro New (March 2020) they have reported that, “A global recession is now a real possibility; central banks worldwide have slashed interest rates to record levels”.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS: The coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic is seen as a historical problem because it is the first-time humanity has encountered such an unprecedented problem. In mid-February, when financial market participants feared that the epidemic would turn into a global pandemic, stock prices plummeted from previous levels. The impact of the pandemic on credit markets, especially in risky segments such as high-yield bonds, leveraged loans and private debt, has been widespread, and the issuance of these segments has largely ceased. Oil prices fell as global demand fell and OPEC + countries failed to reach an agreement to cut production, which further exacerbated the risky

situation. These changing market conditions have led to a return to quality with a sharp decline in yields on secure bonds.

The negative consequences of this pandemic are causing enormous economic hardship to any category of states. According to the world's largest organizations, global economic growth in 2020 will be minus 3%, which is a negative decline. This situation is even worse than in the 2009 global financial crisis. According to the International Monetary Fund in October 2019, the growth forecast for the current year was 6%, but after the onset of the pandemic, the situation has changed radically, and the above data is re-analyzed. The slowdown in economic growth during the pandemic period mainly falls on the group of developed countries, and the growth rate for 2020 was minus 6.1 percent for this group of countries. In most developed countries, the decline is projected for 2020, which is as follows: The United States (-5.9 percent), Japan (-5.2 percent), the United Kingdom (-6.5 percent), Germany (-7.0 percent), France (-7.2 percent), Italy (-9.1 percent), and Spain (-8.0 percent). The impact of this pandemic is much severe in most European countries than in the rest of the world.

Global economic growth is expected to rise to 5.8 percent in 2021, which is a positive indicator, indicating a return to normal levels of economic activity from very low levels of it. While the growth rate in the emerging market and developing economies is 6.6 percent, in developed economies it is 4.5 percent. For comparison, the global growth rate in 2010 rose from minus 0.1 percent in 2009 to 5.4 percent. The resumption of global economic growth in 2021 is due to the complete cessation of the pandemic in the second half of 2020, and the removal of strict restrictions on the pandemic will lead to a gradual return of consumer and investor confidence and which in turn restarts the laws of the market. Significant economic policy measures have been taken to meet the requirements of public health care by limiting to some extent the economic activity and the financial system around the world. The projected recovery assumes that these policy measures will be effective in preventing widespread bankruptcy, rising unemployment, and financial strains of firms. Nevertheless, Figure 1 shows that GDP levels in developed and emerging markets and developing countries are expected to remain below the pre-virus base by the end of 2021. As with the level of decline, there is extreme uncertainty in the recovery of the economy. Failure to implement some of the aspects that support recovery could lead to more negative global economic growth, depending on how the pandemic goes and the severity of the interrelated economic and

financial consequences. For example, a further increase in restrictions in 2020 will lead to a lower rate of economic growth in 2021.

Figure 1. Quarterly World GDP (2019: Q1 = 100; dashed lines indicate estimates from January 2020 World Economic Outlook Update)

Source: IMF staff estimates

At the beginning of the year, a broad sense of optimism emerged against the background of monetary policy supported by financial markets, easing of trade tensions and the first signs of stability in the global economy. However, with the global spread of COVID-19, as the prices of risky assets and commodities began to fall at an unprecedented rate while the prices of safe assets such as gold and the U.S. Treasury rose as investors reassessed the economic consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic. The stock market experienced the fastest decline in history, with the S&P 500 falling about 20 percent in just 16 trading sessions. The decline in asset prices halved the level observed at the worst selling point in 2008–09, and the volatility between asset classes was, in some cases, the last to be observed during the global financial crisis. However, markets have recently reduced some losses as tough policy measures, including the aftermath of the pandemic, have stabilized investor sentiment.

Figure 2. Change in value during coronavirus outbreak of selected stock market indices worldwide from January 1 to March 18, 2020

Source: Statista 2020. Worldwide; Il Sole 24 Ore; January 1 to March 18, 2020
According to Figure 2 above, the world's most popular stock market indices experienced sharp negative changes between January 1 and March 18. In particular, China's CSI 300 stock market index value fell 1.9% as of Jan. 23, followed by a decline of 12.1% from March 6 to March 18. Compared to other stock market indices, the CSI 300 alone saw a 3.4% increase from January 23 to March 6. The NASDAQ 100 and S&P500, two popular U.S. stock market indices, also fell sharply, falling 12.4% and 14.9%, respectively, from March 6 to March 18. The highest declines were recorded in the Italian FTSE MIB and the Greek ATX stock market indices, which were 27.3% and 28.8%, respectively.

Figure 3. Share price index in major Developed and Emerging Economies from April 2019 to April 2020

Source: Statista 2020. Worldwide; April 2019 to April 2020

Figure 3 shows the stock price index of developed and developing countries from April 2019 to April 2020. According to the figure, Brazil's stock price index was at its highest level for the entire period cited, reaching 156.2 in April 2020, up from 191.51 in April 2019. In second place is the Russian stock price index, which during this period was 151.89 and 153.7, respectively, almost reaching the level of Brazil in April. The lowest change during this period was recorded in the Chinese stock price index, which means that although it is at a low level, the country has not seen a sharp rise or fall. It is noteworthy that the stock price index of all these countries rose sharply from January to February 2020, then fell sharply from February to March, and again rose in April.

Figure 4 below shows the percentage of government bond yields in the United States and Germany for 2018-2020 with maturities of 2 and 10 years. In September-November 2018, the yield on bonds of both countries was high with the yield on 10-year U.S. government bonds was above 3%, and the yield on 10-year German government bonds was minus 0.5%. However, the 10-year bonds of the two countries have had a general downward trend during the given period.

Figure 4. Advanced Economy Government Bond Yields (Percent)

Sources: Bloomberg Finance L.P.; and IMF staff calculations.

In March 2020, the yield of these bonds was about 1% in the US and 0.5% in Germany. The yield of 2-year government bonds of these countries was close to the yield of almost 10-year bonds. It is noteworthy that the yield of German 2-year government bonds during the years was only a negative percentage with almost 0.5%.

Figure 5. Advanced Economy Government Bonds (Percent of bonds outstanding, by yield)

Sources: Bloomberg Finance L.P.; and IMF staff calculations.

The changing market conditions in February and March have led investors to move towards safer and more liquid securities. Government bond yields in Germany and the United States declined sharply in net terms (Figure 5). In response to the easing of tight monetary policy by central banks, policy rates in a number of developed countries have approached zero, and government bond

yields are expected to remain low. Government bonds with yields of less than 1 percent (shown in light and dark blue in Figure 5) increased from about 40 percent of bonds outstanding at the end of 2019 to about 80 percent in March.

CONCLUSIONS: This crisis is not like any other one. First, the shock is huge. The costs associated with this emergency and the measures to prevent it are more than the losses caused by the global financial crisis. Second, as in a war or political crisis, there is a strong uncertainty about the duration and intensity of the blow. Third, there are different roles in economic policy in the current context. In normal crises, policymakers try to stimulate economic activity by stimulating aggregate demand as quickly as possible. This time the crisis requires a certain amount of preventive measures. This makes incentive activities more difficult and undesirable, at least for the most affected sectors. Countries are taking drastic measures to maintain economic and financial stability and prevent the emergence of negative macro-financial gaps. Central banks have eased monetary policy and are ensuring the liquidity of the financial system, including influencing the economy through currency exchange lines to maintain credit flows. As a result of these efforts, funding markets have retained their functions and have shown that investor sentiment has improved. Supervisors are urging banks to renegotiate loan terms with those who have problems repaying their debts to help reduce losses and overcome economic hardship. The country's government is helping people and companies through large-scale, timely and targeted financial measures to limit the defaults of firms and households through moratoriums on payments and guaranteed loans. Multilateral cooperation has increased the available resources to support the most vulnerable countries and communities. The IMF, with \$1 trillion in available resources, is actively supporting its member countries. These policies are necessary to ensure that the suspension of production does not lead to further damage to the productive capacity of the economy, the financial system and the structure of society. Once the spread of the virus is under control, policies should be aimed at stimulating economic recovery, as well as assessing and treating the damage caused by the pandemic to the balance sheets of non-financial firms, financial institutions and governments.

References and bibliography:

1. International Monetary Fund, "World Economic Outlook, April 2020: The Great Lockdown" 2020.
2. International Monetary Fund, "Global Financial Stability Report" 2020.
3. Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis, "10-Year Treasury constant maturity rate" accessed March 9, 2020.

4. Mohamed El-Erian, "Coronavirus raises the risk of real trouble in corporate bonds" Financial Times, March 3, 2020.
5. Jeanna Smialek, "Fed official says central bankers are aligned in coronavirus response" New York Times, March 5, 2020.
6. Robin Harding and Hudson Lockett, "BoJ spurs Asia markets rebound with vow to fight coronavirus," Financial Times, March 2, 2020.
7. US Securities and Exchange Commission, "SEC provides conditional regulatory relief and assistance for companies affected by the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19)," March 4, 2020.
8. Euro News. (2020). "What will be the Economic Impact of COVID-19 And Are There Any Silver Linings?"
9. Daily FT. (2020). COVID - 19: The Economic Impact Simplified. Thursday, March, 2020.
10. S & P Global Report. (2020). Corona Virus: Economic & Credit Market Implications. Corona Virus: The Global Impact.
11. statista.com "Coronavirus: Impact on Financial Markets Worldwide" 2020.
12. Nuhu A Sansa "The Impact of the COVID - 19 on the Financial Markets: Evidence from China and USA" Electronic Research Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities. Apr - Jun 2020

